

Amino Acid Esters of Norethindrone as Possible Acrosin Inhibitors[†]

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A series of amino acid esters of norethindrone (I) have been synthesised as possible acrosin inhibitors by reacting different amino acids with I in the presence of equimolar amounts of 4-*N,N*-dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP) and dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC).

THE proteolytic enzyme 'acrosin', present on the sperm head, helps in the removal of zona pellucida, the protecting covering on the ova, during the fertilisation process^{1,2}. Depletion of acrosin from the sperm surface by synthetic^{3,4} and natural proteinase inhibitors⁵⁻⁷ thus effectively block the penetration of the sperm at the surface of the zona. Such anti-acrosin agents, therefore, may find use in the fertility control. However, these enzyme inhibitors interfere with other biological processes as well, limiting their use.

The antiproteolytic activity of some N-protected amino acids and their esters^{8,9} was utilised by Hall *et al.*¹⁰ to produce antifertility effect. In the current study, a series of amino acid esters of norethindrone have been synthesised as pro-drugs. It has been presumed that norethindrone, a potent progestational agent, would act as a carrier of the amino acid residue to the target organs including cervix, vagina and uterine lumen, thus minimising the complications arising due to the presence of enzyme inhibitors in non-target sites. The proteolytic effect of the acrosin released from the sperm surface would hydrolyse the ester linkage and the amino acid residue thus liberated, by virtue of its anti-acrosin activity, would protect the zona pellucida and thereby block the penetration of the sperm at the zona for fertilisation. Norethindrone itself would also contribute toward antifertility activity.

Attempts to esterify norethindrone(I) with various amino acids by standard procedures¹¹⁻¹⁴ were unsuccessful. However, by using N-protected amino acids in the presence of equimolar amounts of DMAP and DCC¹⁵ I could be esterified. Easily removable groups, such as benzyloxycarbonyl (Z) and t-butoxycarbonyl (BOC) were used to protect the amino function. Deblocking was best achieved by treating the ester with anhydrous ether saturated with dry HCl gas. Since esters with free amino groups were found unstable, they were converted to N-acetyl esters *in situ*. Norethindrone esters thus

prepared are given in Table 1. These compounds have been submitted for biological screening and the result will be published separately.

TABLE 1

Compd. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula*
1	H	—	—	—
2	Z-L-Ala	64-66	95.0	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ NO ₂
3	BOC-L-Ala	234-35	90.0	C ₂₈ H ₃₉ NO ₃
4	Ac-L-Ala	97-98	90.0	C ₂₅ H ₃₁ NO ₂
5	BOC-L-Val	69-70	94.1	C ₃₀ H ₄₁ NO ₃
6	Ac-L-Val	110-12	88.2	C ₂₇ H ₃₇ NO ₂
7	BOC-L-Pro	97-98	94.6	C ₃₀ H ₄₁ NO ₃
8	Ac-L-Pro	181-82	95.5	C ₂₇ H ₃₅ NO ₂
9	BOC-L-Phe Ala	92-94	87.5	C ₃₄ H ₄₅ NO ₃
10	Ac-L-Phe Ala	208-10	85.0	C ₃₁ H ₃₇ NO ₂
11	Z-L-Leu	64-66	80.0	C ₃₄ H ₄₅ NO ₃
12	BOC-L-Leu	84-86	85.0	C ₃₁ H ₄₃ NO ₃
13	Ac-L-Leu	193-95	90.2	C ₂₈ H ₃₉ NO ₂
14	BOC-L-I Leu	87-88	85.0	C ₃₁ H ₄₃ NO ₃
15	Ac-L-I Leu	91-93	81.3	C ₂₈ H ₃₉ NO ₂
16	BOC-L(p Ac)Tyr	102-104	80.0	C ₃₆ H ₄₇ NO ₃
17	Ac-L(p Ac)Tyr	207-208	70.0	C ₃₃ H ₄₃ NO ₂
18	BOC-L-Try	208-210	88.0	C ₃₆ H ₄₇ N ₂ O ₃
19	Ac-L-Try	148-50	78.7	C ₃₃ H ₄₃ N ₂ O ₂
20	BOC-L(ε.BOC)ORn	87-88	80.0	C ₃₆ H ₄₇ N ₂ O ₃
21	Ac-L(ε.Ac)ORn	75-77	70.0	C ₃₃ H ₄₃ N ₂ O ₂
22	BOC-L(ε.BOC)Lys	88-90	88.0	C ₃₉ H ₅₁ N ₃ O ₃
23	Ac-L(ε.Ac)Lys	74-77	90.0	C ₃₆ H ₄₇ N ₃ O ₂
24	BOC-L-Met	78-80	90.0	C ₃₀ H ₄₁ N ₂ O ₃
25	Ac-L-Met	98-100	89.0	C ₂₇ H ₃₇ N ₂ O ₂
26	4-BOC.NH-(CH ₂) ₈ .CO	oil	90.0	C ₃₉ H ₅₁ NO ₃
27	4-Ac.NH-(OH) ₂ .CO	58-60	95.9	C ₂₆ H ₃₅ NO ₂
28	6-BOC.NH-(OH) ₂ .CO	oil	85.0	C ₃₁ H ₄₃ NO ₃
29	6-Ac.NH-(OH) ₂ .CO	105-107	95.0	C ₂₈ H ₃₉ NO ₂

* All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N analyses.

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Experimental

All melting points were taken in sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer. ^1H nmr spectra, in CDCl_3 (unless otherwise mentioned), were run on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard (chemical shift in δ ppm). Uv spectra (methanol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 202 ultraviolet-visible spectrometer. Mass spectra were obtained using a JEOL JMS-D 300 spectrometer.

N-Benzyloxy-, *N*-acetyl- and *N,N*-di-*t*-butoxycarbonylamino acids were prepared by the standard procedures¹⁶⁻¹⁸. *N*-*t*-Butoxycarbonylamino acids were obtained by the method of Schnabel¹⁹. Preparations of *N*-*t*-butoxycarbonyl-4-aminobutyric acid and *N*-*t*-butoxycarbonyl-6-aminocaproic acid are described.

Typical examples :

N-*t*-Butoxycarbonyl-4-aminobutyric acid : A mixture of 4-aminobutyric acid (2 g, 19.40 mmol), *t*-butyl azidofornate (3 ml, 21.18 mmol), 4*N* NaOH (5 ml), dioxane (10 ml) and water (10 ml) was stirred at room temperature for 4 h. The pH of the reaction mixture was maintained at 9-10 by occasional addition of 4*N* NaOH. The mixture was diluted with water (50 ml) and extracted with ethyl acetate (2 × 10 ml). The aqueous layer was cooled and acidified to pH 2 with citric acid. After saturating with sodium chloride the mixture was extracted with ethyl acetate (4 × 20 ml). The organic layer was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent distilled off under reduced pressure to give an oil which solidified upon standing (3.6 g, 91.3%), m.p. 53-4° (Found : C, 53.2; H, 8.3; N, 6.5. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_4$ requires : C, 53.2; H, 8.4; N, 6.9%); ν_{max} 3340 (NH) and 1700 cm^{-1} (CONH); δ 1.34 (9H, s, $\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 1.72 (2H, m, 3- CH_2), 2.27 (2H, m, 2- CH_2), 3.04 (2H, m, 4- CH_2), 5.00 (1H, br, NH) and 8.80 (1H, br, CO_2H).

N-*t*-Butoxycarbonyl-6-aminocaproic acid : It was prepared following the above procedure from 6-aminocaproic acid, (93.6%), m.p. 41-2° (Found : C, 56.8; H, 8.9; N, 6.3. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{21}\text{NO}_4$ requires : C, 57.1; H, 9.2; N, 6.1%). ν_{max} (neat) 3340 (NH) and 1700 cm^{-1} (CONH); δ 1.28 (9H, s, $\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 2.08 (2H, m, 2- CH_2), 2.90 (2H, m, 6- CH_2), 4.56 (1H, br, NH) and 8.78 (1H, br, CO_2H).

17-(*N*-Acetylpyrrolidino-2'-carbonyl)oxy-19-norpregn-4-en-20-yn-3-one (8) : A mixture of norethindrone (I; 0.50 g, 1.68 mmol), *N*-acetyl-L-proline (0.40 g, 2.55 mmol), DCC (0.42 g, 2.03 mmol) and DMAP (0.225 g, 1.84 mmol) in dry CH_2Cl_2 (20 ml) was allowed to stand at room temperature for 16 h. Dicyclohexylurea was filtered off; the filtrate extracted with 4*N* HCl (4 × 5 ml), 1*N* Na_2CO_3 solution (4 × 5 ml) and finally with brine and dried

(Na_2SO_4). On removal of the solvent *in vacuo* it yielded a residue which on crystallisation from EtOAc gave 8, ν_{max} 1745 (OCO), 1660 (3-CO) and 1620 cm^{-1} (C=C); λ_{max} 245 nm; δ 0.89 (3H, s, 18- CH_3), 1.98 (3H, s, COCH_3), 2.49 (1H, s, C=CH), 3.47 (3H, m, 5'- CH_2), 4.27 (1H, m, 2'-CH) and 5.70 (1H, s, 4-H); m/z 437 (M^+).

Norethindrone-L-2-acetamidopropanoate (4) : To a solution of norethindrone-L-2-*t*-butoxycarbonylamino propanoate (0.7 g) dry CH_2Cl_2 (5 ml) was added ethereal HCl (5 ml) and the solution stirred at room temperature for 4 h. To the residue obtained on removal of the solvents *in vacuo* pyridine (5 ml) and Ac_2O (2 ml) were added and the mixture left at room temperature for 2 h. Pyridine and Ac_2O were removed under vacuum and water added to the residue. It was extracted with EtOAc (3 × 20 ml) and the organic layer washed successively with 2*N* HCl (2 × 5 ml), aqueous NaHCO_3 (3 × 5 ml), water (4 × 5 ml); dried (Na_2SO_4) and solvent distilled off. The residue thus obtained was purified by column chromatography followed by crystallisation from ethyl acetate; ν_{max} 3330 (NH), 1745 (OCO), 1660 (3-CO) and 1620 cm^{-1} (C=C); λ_{max} 243 nm; δ 0.86 (3H, s, 18- CH_3), 1.30 (3H, d, J 8 Hz, CHCH_3), 1.91 (3H, s, NHCOCH_3), 2.51 (1H, s, C=H), 4.42 (1H, m, COCH), 5.70 (1H, s, 4-H) and 6.28 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, NH); m/z 411 (M^+).

References

1. J. YAMANE, *Cytologia*, 1935, 6, 283.
2. L. M. BURUIANA, *Naturwissenschaften*, 1956, 43, 528.
3. L. J. D. ZENEVELD, R. T. ROBERTSON and W. L. WILLIAMS, *FEBS Lett.*, 1970, 11, 345.
4. S. O. NEWELL, K. L. POLAKOSKI and W. L. WILLIAMS, *Proc. Int. Congr. Anim. Reprod. Artif. Insemin.*, 7th., 1972.
5. L. J. D. ZENEVELD, R. T. ROBERTSON, M. KESSLER and W. L. WILLIAMS, *J. Reprod. Fertil.*, 1971, 25, 887.
6. L. J. D. ZENEVELD, K. L. POLAKOSKI, R. T. ROBERTSON and W. L. WILLIAMS, *Proc. Int. Res. Conf. Protease Inhibitors*, 1st., 1970.
7. R. STAMBAUGH, B. G. BRACKELT and L. MASTROIANNI, *Biol. Reprod.*, 1969, 1, 223.
8. L. J. LOEFFLER, Z. SAJADI and I. H. HALL, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1977, 20, 1578.
9. L. J. LOEFFLER, Z. SAJADI and I. H. HALL, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1977, 20, 1581.
10. I. H. HALL, J. H. DREW, Z. SAJADI and L. J. LOEFFLER, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1979, 68, 696.
11. L. F. FIESER, "Experiments in Organic Chemistry", D. O. Heath, Boston, 1977, p. 77.
12. K. HOLMBERG and B. HANSEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1979, 33, 410.
13. W. SZMJA, *Synthesis*, 1980, 402.
14. A. A. L. GUNATILAKA and S. SOTHRERSWARAN, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1978, 980.

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15. K. LAL, P. L. KOLRY and S. RAY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1982, 21, 682.
16. J. P. GREENSTEIN and M. WINITS, "Chemistry of Amino Acids", John Wiley, New York, 1961, pp. 887, 2195
17. G. R. PETTIT and S. K. GUPTA, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1967, 45, 1561.
18. E. SANDRIN and R. A. BOISSONNAS, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1963, 46, 1637.
19. E. SCHNABEL, *Iustus Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 1967, 702, 188.